

USE OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article describes the essence of the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in education and its role and importance in improving the quality of education. Also, this article discusses the effectiveness of using innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process and offers suggestions for a new approach to the educational process in higher education institutions.

Key words: innovation, pedagogical technology, quality of education, IT specialists, innovative approach.

Introduction:

The role of the education system in accelerating the socio-economic development of our country and ensuring its economic security is incomparable. Among the global trends such as the internationalization of education, the international mobility of students, the rapid change of the educational program, the issue of ensuring the quality of education is gaining special importance. Modern socio-economic conditions and the high demands placed on the spiritual-ethical, intellectual and professional potential of future specialists put the task of training quality personnel who can meet international requirements before educational institutions. In order to fulfill these tasks, it is necessary to use innovative pedagogical technologies in education. However, modern trends in the educational system, especially the innovative pedagogical technologies used in the educational system of developed foreign countries, are being relatively slowly assimilated.

Pedagogical technology is a system of modern organization of the educational process, which ensures the necessary quality of education and meets the requirements of accelerated scientific and technical development, aimed at the improvement of educational forms, teaching processes with techniques and It is a consistent method of creation and implementation in human factors, through their joint actions. The use of innovative pedagogical technologies in the educational process is the demand of the times.

A systematic method of creation, application and determination of all processes of teaching and knowledge acquisition, with the task of optimizing educational forms, taking into account pedagogical technology-technical resources, people and their interaction.

In the educational process, teaching using new innovative techniques and technologies, conducting training using laboratory rooms equipped with the latest techniques, providing information about the latest innovations in the specialty, for example, in the field of chemistry. , citing examples from world experience motivates students to be educated in the spirit of innovation.

In our opinion, students' latent ability to create innovation will be awakened in the educational process if they first arouse interest and motivation, and then create a competitive

environment. The goal would be achieved faster if students were given examples of people who achieved success in creating science and innovation, and if possible, invited one of them to the class as a role model, or if it was arranged to bring students to the innovation center on excursions.

We believe that if we organize an excursion for students to the innovation fair and IT parks in the region, we will increase the achievements in connecting the theoretical knowledge given in education with practice.

In accordance with their specialization, we have already started sending students to the production enterprises and factories of our country for internships in our institutes. But our suggestion is that the scientific research institutions of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan invited a representative to the institute as an honored guest, and the privilege of listening to his speech at the seminar and the scope of the impressions received from it would have encouraged talented students.

Innovative education (see "innovation" - creation of new ideas, norms, rules in the learner, advanced ideas, norms, rules created by other people qualities related to natural reception, education that creates the possibility of formation of skills.

The technologies used in the process of innovative education are called innovative educational technologies or educational innovations. While organizing a lesson based on innovative technologies, the teacher can use various technical tools (computer, projector, electronic board, etc.) and conduct lessons based on interactive methods. Innovative technologies arise from the fact that the teacher is not satisfied with his work, he tries to introduce innovations to improve it.

"Activity renewal is carried out in 3 stages, i.e. preparation, planning and implementation stages," said the famous pedagogue A. Nikolskaya.

The main goal of innovative technologies is to achieve cooperation between the teacher and the student, to make students interested in science, to change the attitude towards education, to acquire the ability to apply the learned knowledge in social conditions, information communication technologies and didactic materials can be combined with the subject.

Nowadays, the interest and attention to the use of interactive methods, innovative technologies, pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day, one of the reasons for this is that until now, traditional education If students are taught to acquire only ready-made knowledge in lim, modern technologies teach them to search for the acquired knowledge by themselves, to study and analyze independently, and even to draw their own conclusions. Knowledge, experience, and interactive methods of pedagogical technology and pedagogic skills ensure that pupils-students acquire knowledgeable, mature skills.

Innovative pedagogical technologies are very important in the educational process for training modern specialists who will be in demand in the labor market in the future.

In order to train modern personnel, it is necessary for the pedagogue himself to be aware of the latest scientific achievements, the innovations of the field he is teaching, and to conduct classes based on the latest pedagogical technologies, using modern ICT tools.

In the concept of development of higher education until 2030, it is aimed to include higher education institutions of our country in the ranks of international 1000 educational

institutions. However, the study of the international experience of innovative pedagogical technologies and their implementation is being carried out relatively slowly.

To clarify our point, if we give an example of different types of training courses for applicants, the goal of a preparatory course of a pedagogue is not to get into the ranks of the best, but to achieve the intended goal of the students who are the result of their work. For example, the students of the IELTS courses in English will get this certificate with high scores, and the entrants in the subjects will enter the higher education institution of their choice with high results - this is the primary goal of the pedagogue. and the achievement of this goal alone makes it one of the best courses. All these achievements depend not only on the strong knowledge of that pedagogue, but also on the pedagogical technology of delivering this knowledge.

We believe that in higher education institutions, the goal should be connected with the career achievements of the specialists trained by this institution and the fact that they are mature staff with high demand. Because the quality of any activity is reflected in its result. The role of teaching through innovative pedagogical technologies in the quality implementation of the educational process is incomparable. It is necessary to provide such high-quality, practice-related education in the training of a specialist in a specific direction in HEIs, so that graduates do not need to go to additional courses during the process of entering a job.

IT specialists are the most in-demand profession now and in the future. These areas should be opened more in higher education institutions and pedagogues should have deep knowledge and high pedagogical skills and teach on the basis of innovative technologies in order to train mature personnel in this field. In order to achieve success in such fields, we believe that higher education institutions equipped with modern techniques and technologies and teaching on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies are definitely among the best institutions. When working on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies, the teacher must have an understanding of innovative activities. According to its essence, innovative activity consists of scientific research, creating developments, conducting experimental work, creating a new improved product based on the use of scientific and technical achievements.

The innovative activity of a teacher is determined by:

- readiness to use the innovation;
- acceptance of pedagogical innovations;
- level of innovation;
- development of communication skills;
- creativity.

Innovative activity is an activity aimed at solving complex problems that arise as a result of the incompatibility of new social requirements with traditional norms or the denial of existing ideas by newly formed ideas.

Innovative activity requires the acquisition of knowledge, skills, competence, supplementing practical activities with theoretical knowledge, development of knowledge, design, communicative speech and organizational skills based on directing the pedagogue's spiritual, mental, and physical strength to a specific goal.

At the 1st stage, ready-made methodological descriptions (existing innovation, for example, used in foreign experience, but new for us) are used.

In the 2nd stage, the pedagogue introduces his new ideas and methods into the existing system. To determine the innovative approach of pedagogues

In the 3rd stage, he systematizes the content, forms and methods of implementing the idea, innovative method created in the second stage in the institution where he operates.

At the 4th stage, the pedagogue creates his own concept (set of ideas) or methodology related to teaching and training.

At these stages, if a pedagogue implements innovative approaches and introduces innovations in pedagogical technologies, the quality of education will definitely increase. In general, great attention is paid to the field of education and innovations in our country.

It is also a complex process for teachers to decide on an innovative approach, which takes place in several stages. According to experts, the innovative e-textbook imitates the human intelligence's ability to remember a large amount of information and search through this information through the association of communication and thought processes. In other words, an innovative e-textbook is a complex educational material system that incorporates a lot of statistical and dynamic information and has a generalized network structure: video, executable program, and animation.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5264 of November 29, 2017 "On the establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and [1] No. PQ-3416 of Uzbekistan of November 30, 2017 In accordance with the Decision of the President of the Republic "On the establishment of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan", the ministry of the same name was established, and among its tasks is the introduction of innovations into the social development, including the education and health care system. is also included.

Conclusion:

To sum up, if the use of innovative pedagogical technologies in education increases the quality of education, innovative technologies are the driving force of educational development. The future of every society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part of it and a vital necessity. Today, reforming and improving the continuous education system of our country, which is on the path of independent development, raising it to a new level of quality, introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into it, and increasing the effectiveness of education have been raised to the level of state policy.

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